

Supporting Information

Ring Size Determines the Conformation, Global Aromaticity and Photophysical Properties of Macrocyclic Oligofurans

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S1. General Information

The reagents and chemicals used here are commercially available and were used without further purification unless otherwise stated. Flash chromatography (FC) was performed using CombiFlash SiO₂ columns. The compound *N*-(2-octyldodecyl)-5,5'-dibromo-2,2'-bifuran-3,3'-dicarboximide ((**L-1BFI**)Br₂) was synthesized according to the procedures detailed in the literature.¹ ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded in solution on Bruker-AVIII 400 MHz and 500 MHz spectrometers using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as the external standard. The spectra were recorded using chloroform-*d* and dichloromethane-*d*₂ as solvents. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ units. UV-vis absorption and fluorescence spectra of synthesized compounds were recorded on an Agilent Technologies Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer. Fluorescence measurements were carried out with a Horiba Scientific Fluoromax-4 spectrofluorometer. Preparative size exclusion chromatography was performed in chloroform solution at room temperature using a Recycling Preparative HPLC LaboACE LC-7080 through JAIGEL-2HR and JAIGEL-2.5HR columns connected in series.

S2. Synthesis

Synthesis of BFI macrocycles (**C-nBFI**)

The reaction was carried out in a glovebox with N₂ under atmosphere. A solution of bis(1,5-cyclooctadiene)nickel(0) [Ni(COD)₂] (780 mg, 2.8 mmol) and 2,2'-dipyridyl (168 mg, 1.1 mmol) in dry THF (210 mL) was stirred for 30 min at room temperature inside an oven-dried 500 mL flask. (**L-1BFI**)Br₂ (190 mg, 0.3 mmol) in dry THF (40 mL) was then added dropwise using a dropping funnel over 3 hours. The reaction mixture was stirred for 72 hours at room temperature in the dark. The solvent was evaporated under vacuum and the crude product was purified by flash column chromatography on silica gel using 10% ethyl acetate in *n*-hexane as eluent to give a mixture of macrocycles. The mixture was then separated by GPC using chloroform as the eluent to give **C-3BFI** (5.0 mg, 4%), **C-4BFI** (44.4 mg, 31%), **C-5BFI** (15.8 mg, 11%), and **C-6BFI** (20.0 mg, 14%).

C-3BFI:

¹H NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ 6.98 (s, 6H), 4.22 (d, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 6H), 1.82 (m, 3H), 1.40 – 1.15 (m, 96H), 0.87 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 18H). **¹³C NMR** (126 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ 160.16, 145.81, 143.24, 122.26, 110.29, 36.59, 32.10, 32.07, 31.87, 30.23, 29.83, 29.81, 29.78, 29.73, 29.52, 29.49, 26.66, 22.85, 14.28. **HRMS** (MALDI) calcd for C₉₀H₁₂₉N₃O₁₂ 1443.957, found 1443.988 (M)⁺.

C-4BFI:

The NMR spectra matches literature data.²

C-5BFI:

¹H NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ 7.47 (s, 10H), 4.24 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 10H), 1.90 (m, 5H), 1.40 – 1.15 (m, 160H), 0.85 (t, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 30H). **HRMS** (MALDI) calcd for C₁₅₀H₂₁₅N₅O₂₀ 2406.595, found 2406.588 (M)⁺.

C-6BFI:

¹H NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ 7.42 (s, 12H), 4.23 (d, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 12H), 1.87 (m, 6H), 1.40 – 1.15 (m, 192H), 0.85 (t, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 36H). **¹³C NMR** (126 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ 159.93, 144.67, 142.88, 122.61, 113.31, 77.41, 77.16, 76.91, 36.51, 32.09, 32.07, 31.81, 30.23, 29.87, 29.85, 29.83, 29.82, 29.80, 29.77, 29.75, 29.52, 29.50, 26.59, 22.83, 14.26. **HRMS** (MALDI) calcd for C₁₈₀H₂₅₈N₆O₂₄ 2887.914, found 2888.323 (M)⁺.

S3. Spectra

S3.1. NMR

Figure S1. ¹H-NMR spectrum of C-3BFI in CDCl₃ measured at 298 K.

Figure S2. ¹³C-NMR spectrum of **C-3BFI** in CDCl₃ measured at 298 K.

Figure S3. COSY-NMR spectrum of **C-3BFI** in CDCl₃ measured at 298 K.

Figure S4. HSQC-NMR spectrum of **C-3BFI** in CDCl_3 measured at 298 K.

Figure S5. HMBC-NMR spectrum of **C-3BFI** in CDCl₃ measured at 298 K.

Figure S6. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of **C-5BFI** in CDCl_3 measured at 298 K.

Figure S7. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of **C-6BFI** in CDCl_3 measured at 298 K.

Figure S8. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of C-6BFI in CDCl_3 measured at 298 K.

Figure S9. COSY-NMR spectrum of **C-6BFI** in CDCl_3 measured at 298 K.

Figure S10. HSQC-NMR spectrum of **C-6BFI** in CDCl_3 measured at 298 K.

Figure S11. HMBC-NMR spectrum of **C-6BFI** in CDCl₃ measured at 298 K.

Figure S12. ¹H-NMR spectrum of **C-6BFI** in CD₂Cl₂ measured between 10°C and -80°C.

Coalescence can be observed for the β-protons peak (7.41 ppm) at -5°C. The energy barrier (ΔG^\ddagger) was calculated to be 13.0 kcal mol⁻¹ using a derivative of the Eyring equation,³ where temperature T=268.15 K and the NMR shift separation of the signals $\Delta\nu = 59.34$ Hz.

Equation S1.
$$\Delta G^\ddagger = RT_c [22.96 + \ln (T_c / \Delta\nu)]$$

S3.2. MALDI-TOF

Figure S13. MALDI-TOF spectrum of **C-3BFI**. (Top) full spectra and (bottom) excerpt of target region.

Figure S14. MALDI-TOF spectrum of **C-5BFI**. (Top) full spectra and (bottom) excerpt of target region.

Figure S15. MALDI-TOF spectrum of **C-6BFI**. (Top) full spectra and (bottom) excerpt of target region.

S3.3. Absorption and Fluorescence Spectra

S3.3.1. Variable-Temperature Fluorescence Spectra

Figure S16. Emission spectra of **C-3BFI** excited at 390 nm at 25 °C (black), 40 °C (red), and 62 °C (blue). The emission band at 630 nm is not affected by varying the temperature, which excludes the possibility of an excimer, leading us to conclude that this band corresponds to the forbidden $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition.

Figure S17. Emission spectra of **C-4BFI** excited at 400 nm at 25 °C (black), 50 °C (red), and 62 °C (blue). The emission band at 670 nm is not affected by varying the temperature, which excludes the possibility of an excimer, leading us to conclude that this band corresponds to the forbidden $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition.

S3.3.2. Transient absorption measurements

Transient absorption (TA) measurement: TA measurements were carried out using a homemade amplified Ti-sapphire laser system. The fundamental output centre at 800 nm has ~30 fs pulse duration and ~1 mJ/pulse energy. All the measurements were carried out at 720 Hz. Half of the fundamental was used to pump an optical parametric amplifier (OPA) with an output signal at around 1250 nm. Half of the 1250 nm laser was focused on a 2 mm CaF₂ crystal to generate a white light supercontinuum probe pulse. Next, the other half of the fundamental was used to generate the pump laser. A 400 nm laser was obtained from the second harmonic (SH) of the fundamental. SH was generated on a 0.1 mm type I BBO crystal. To generate a 480 nm pump, we used another OPA that has an output centre at 1160 nm. The 1160 nm output was mixed with the 800 nm on a 0.3 mm type-II BBO crystal. Next, individual pump pulses were compressed in a grating compressor, which produces ~35 fs pulse. The pump and probe pulses focus on a sample cell with a 0.5 mm quartz window and 0.4 mm path length. The sample cell was rapidly rotated to limit the photodecomposition. Transmitted probe pulses were dispersed in an imaging spectrograph (Oriel) onto a charged-coupled device (CCD) camera (Andor Technology). Half of the pump pulses were blocked by a chopper running at 360 Hz, and difference absorption (ΔOD) spectra were obtained by $\Delta OD = \log\left(\frac{I_{NP}}{I_P}\right)$ at each pump-probe delay. I_P and I_{NP} refer to probe intensity in the presence and absence of a pump pulse, respectively. A computer-controlled precision optical delay delayed the probe pulse.

We carried out all TA measurements in two set by varying the pump polarization with respect to probe polarization to evaluate anisotropy(r) and magic angle ΔOD (ΔOD_{MA}) spectrum. In one set of measurements, both the pump and probe have identical vertical polarization (VV). Similarly, on another set probe is vertical, but the pump is horizontal (VH). All the TA data presented in this article are for magic-angle polarization. $m\Delta OD$ stands for magic-angle polarization absorption difference(ΔOD_{MA}) times 10^{-3} .

$$r = \frac{\Delta OD_{VV} - \Delta OD_{VH}}{\Delta OD_{VV} + 2 \times \Delta OD_{VH}}$$
$$\Delta OD_{MA} = \frac{\Delta OD_{VV} + 2 \times \Delta OD_{VH}}{3}$$

The coherent modulations present in the TA data are isolated by taking the residual following a polynomial fitting. Isolated modulations are subjected to the Fourier transform in LabVIEW using the inbuilt FFT algorithm. The data is zero-padded to the array length of 1024. In addition, a blank TA measurement is carried out with the chloroform solvent, and the TA data is Fourier transformed a similar way, excluding the polynomial fitting step. The FFT of chloroform shows peaks at 368 and 671 cm^{-1} , which agrees with the Raman vibrational frequency of chloroform (**Figure S21**). FFT of **C-3BFI** shows various low-frequency vibrational activity surround the narrow excited absorption peak at 580 nm, suggesting an excited state vibrational mode. In addition, the Raman modes of solvent dominate the rest of the TA spectrum. Interestingly TA data of **C-5BFI** only shows Raman active vibrational frequency of the solvent, which suggests that it might present as a collection of conformers.

Figure S18. (a) Spectral evolution of **C-3BFI** at 580 nm. The TA increases gradually and settles in few picoseconds. (b) Spectral evolution of **C-3BFI** at 580 nm and monoexponential fit of its decay. In order to avoid the initial rise, we exponentially fitted the decay starting from 50 ps. The monoexponential fitting provides a 1.3 ns lifetime.

Figure S19. (a) Spectral evolution of **C-5BFI** at 930 nm after 480 nm excitation. The TA show a rapid decay process. (b) Spectral evolution of **C-5BFI** at 930 nm after 480 nm excitation and exponential fitting of the decay.

Figure S20. TA Difference spectrum between a pair of delays for **C-5BFI**. The dynamic difference spectra for early delays black and red show identical appearance, which indicates that the same process continues over this time. On the other hand, the pink spectrum contains a significant vibronic structure, and it is positive in the ground state absorption range. The pink difference spectrum suggests the ground state bleach recovery following excited state decay. In view of the different appearances of the early (black) and late (pink) difference spectrum, we assign the initial process as a spectral shift and the late process as excited state (S_1) decay.

Figure S21. Magic-angle polarization TA Spectra of **C-5BFI** at various pump-probe delays upon 400 nm excitation (solid line) and 480 nm (dotted line).

Figure S22. (a) Spectral evolution of **C-5BFI** at 930 nm after 400 nm excitation and exponential fitting of the decay. (b) Spectral evolution of **C-5BFI** at 930 nm after 400 nm excitation and exponential fitting of the decay.

Figure S23. Dynamic difference spectrum of **C-5BFI** excited at 400 nm (black) and 480 nm (red).

Figure S24. (a) Depolarization decay of **C-3BFI** at 580 nm. The exponential fitting provides initial anisotropy of 0.1 and a depolarization lifetime of 0.8 ns. (b) Depolarization decay of **C-5BFI** at 930 nm excited at 480 nm. The observed anisotropy at 200 fs is 0.23. The exponential fitting provides starting anisotropy of 0.16 and a depolarization lifetime of 1.4 ns. The fitting is carried out starting from 100 ps to avoid the initial process. The initial process causes anisotropy reduction from 0.23 to 0.16. It is most likely due to structural reorganization rather than rotational depolarization.

Figure S25. 2D colour map of the FFT, the x-axis represents probe wavelength, the y-axis represents the FFT wavenumber, and colour represents the FFT power in arbitrary units. Chloroform shows activity at 368 and 671 cm^{-1} (a); **C-3BFI** shows various Raman active modes predominantly at the low-frequency region (b). **C-5BFI** failed to show activity besides the solvent (c). In the view of a very broad TA absorption band and lack of vibrational activity, we suggest that **C-5BFI** exist as a collection of conformers.

Table S1. Singlet lifetimes, initial anisotropy and depolarization lifetimes of **C-3BFI** and **C-5BFI**.

	C-3BFI	C-5BFI (excited at 480 nm)	C-5BFI (excited at 400 nm)
Singlet lifetime	1.3 ns	2.5 ns	2 ns
Initial anisotropy	0.1	0.23	0.06
Depolarization lifetime	0.8 ns	1.4 ns	-

S4. Computational Results

All calculations were carried out with the Gaussian 16 series of programs⁴ using density function theory (DFT). Becke's three-parameter exchange functional combined with the Lee-Yang-Parr correlation functional (B3LYP) and with the 6-311G(d) basis set was used for all calculations. The B3LYP functional was chosen to enable us to conduct a valid comparison with our previous computational studies of macrocyclic oligofurans.⁵ No symmetry restrictions were applied in any of the optimal geometries presented. The optimal geometries for all structures were confirmed as minima by frequency calculations. No negative frequencies were found for any stationary points presented in this work.

S4.1. Absolute Energies

Table S2. Absolute energies for all structures presented in this work.

Molecule	Energy (Hartree)
L-3BFI	-2217.291702
L-4BFI	-2955.993414
L-5BFI	-3694.695241
L-6BFI	-4433.397026
C-3BFI (D_{3h} symmetry)	-2216.069377
C-3BFI	-2216.069355
[C-3BFI]²⁺	-2215.445866
C-4BFI (D_{4h} symmetry)	-2954.791435
C-4BFI	-2954.79176
[C-4BFI]²⁺	-2954.21046
C-5BFI (D_{5h} symmetry)	-3693.436003
C-5BFI	-3693.469036
[C-5BFI]²⁺	-3692.891804
C-6BFI (D_{6h} symmetry)	-4432.036071
C-6BFI	-4432.184905

S4.2. NICS

Nucleus-independent chemical shifts (NICS) calculations can be used to estimate the aromaticity based on the existence and effect of a ring current; negative NICS values indicate an aromatic system, whereas positive values suggest an antiaromatic system.

Figure S26. NICS(1) values averaged for all furan subunits in **C-3-6BFI** (red) and the minimal (outermost) and maximal (innermost) furan subunits of their linear analogues **L-3-6BFI** (blue). Red error bars represent standard deviations from averaged values. Values for linear oligomers (blue) are connected to indicate that this is a range. The innermost values for the linear oligomers represent the furans that are the most quinoid in nature, and the outermost values represent the most aromatic furans.

Figure S27. NICS_{zz} map on the Y=0 plane of **C-3BFI**.

Figure S28. NICS_{zz} map on the Y=0 plane of **[C-3BFI]²⁺**.

Figure S29. NICS_{zz} map on the Y=0 plane of **C-4BFI**.

Figure S30. NICS_{zz} map on the Y=0 plane of **[C-4BFI]²⁺**.

S4.3. ACID plots

Figure S31. ACID plot of **C-3BFI**.

Figure S32. ACID plot of [C-3BFI]²⁺.

Figure S33. ACID plot of **C-4BFI**.

Figure S34. ACID plot of $[\text{C-4BFI}]^{2+}$.

Figure S35. ACID plot of **C-5BFI**

Figure S36. ACID plot of **C-6BFI**.

S4.4. GMMX conformations

Figure S37. Overlay of all 15 structures of **C-5BFI** obtained from GMMX.

Figure S38. Overlay of 448 structures of **C-6BFI** obtained from GMMX. Three additional figure-eight-shaped structures were omitted from the overlay for clarity (because their positions were translated in relation to those of the other structures). All 451 conformers were figure-eight shaped.

S4.5. TD-DFT calculation of **C-3-6BFI** (6-311g(d))

All TD-DFT calculations were performed using the 6-311g(d) basis set. For each member of the **C-3-6BFI** series, we present four sets of calculated spectra, calculated using the B3LYP, CAM-B3LYP, LC-wHPBE, and wB97XD functionals, respectively. The experimental absorption spectrum (normalized) is displayed as the black line, and the dashed blue line is the calculated spectrum. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S39. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/B3LYP/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-3BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S40. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/CAM-B3LYP/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-3BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S41. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/LC-wHPBE/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-3BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S42. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/wB97XD/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-3BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S43. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/B3LYP/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-4BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S44. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/CAM-B3LYP/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-4BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S45. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/LC-wHPBE/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-4BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S46. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/wB97XD/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-4BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S47. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/B3LYP/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-5BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S48. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/CAM-B3LYP/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-5BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S49. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/LC-wHPBE/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-5BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S50. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/wB97XD/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-5BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S51. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/B3LYP/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-6BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S52. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/CAM-B3LYP/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-6BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S53. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/LC-wHPBE/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-6BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

Figure S54. Experimental (black) and calculated (TD-DFT/wB97XD/6-311g(d)) spectra of **C-6BFI**. Oscillator strengths and wavelengths are represented by the blue bars.

S4.6. β -protons in dimer model

Calculated NMR chemical shifts showed the same trend as the shifts measured experimentally (Figure 1c). The chemical shift increases as the macrocycle size increases from the trimer to pentamer before slightly decreasing again for **C-6BFI**. To identify the cause of this trend, we examined the full **C-nBFI** molecule and a dimer isolated from each of their rings. To derive the dimer, we removed all but two **BFI** units from each optimized **C-nBFI** structure, and then proceeded to calculate the NMR for each dimer without any further structural optimization. A difference is observed between the dimer and the full macrocycle only for the (quasi)planar **C-3BFI** and **C-4BFI** molecules. Furthermore, the difference between the chemical shifts of **C-3BFI** and **C-4BFI** is larger than the difference between the dimers isolated from each of their rings. Consequently, we conclude that the spectral trend of increasing chemical shift with increasing macrocycle size is not solely a reflection of differences in the geometries of the series members, but also reflects differences in the distances between the β -protons of neighbouring **BFI** units as well as the effect of the (anti)aromaticity of the global ring current.

Figure S55. Calculated (DFT/B3LYP/6-311g(d) with GD3) chemical shift of the β -protons of **C-nBFI** (blue) and the dimers (comprising two **BFI** units) isolated from these macrocycles (orange).

S4.7. Bisecting angle of **BFI**

The bisecting angle of the **BFI** building block was calculated using the optimized structure of α,α' -dimethyl-bifuranimide-methyl (**DM-BFI-Me**).

Figure S56. Bisecting angle of α,α' -dimethyl-bifuranimide-methyl (**DM-BFI-Me**). The angle is defined as the angle between the two vectors of the bonds between the α and methyl carbons (dashed lines) and is calculated to be ca. 81° .

S4.8. Bent angle of **C-4BFI**

Figure S57. Dihedral angle between the plains created by two opposing **BFI** units in **C-4BFI**. The planes and angle were calculated using the Mercury software.

S5. Electrochemistry

For electrochemical measurements, dichloromethane containing 0.1 M tetra-n-butylammonium perchlorate (TBAPC) was used as a solvent. Ag/AgCl was used as a reference electrode by dipping a silver wire in an aqueous solution of FeCl₃ and HCl. Platinum-disk and platinum-wire electrodes were applied as working and counter electrodes, respectively. All electrochemical measurements were performed under a dry nitrogen atmosphere and were externally calibrated against the E^{1/2} of the Fc/Fc⁺ redox couple.

Figure S58. Cyclic voltammetry of **C-3BFI** in dichloromethane as solvent and 0.1 M TBAPC as electrolyte, referenced against the Fc/Fc⁺ redox couple (scan rate 100 mV/s).

S6. X-Ray Data for C-3BFI

A single crystal suitable for X-ray diffraction was coated with Paratone oil (Hampton Research, CA, USA), mounted on a MiTeGen loop and flash frozen in liquid nitrogen. Diffraction data were recorded on Rigaku Synergy R system equipped with a Rigaku HyPix Arc150 detector. Data were measured with Cu α radiation at 100(2) K. The data were collected and processed with CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.111a (Rigaku OD, 2021) The crystals were twinned and the data were treated as a two component twin. The structure was determined by direct methods using SHELXT-2018 with SHELXL-2013 and SHELXL-2016/4. The structure is triclinic P-1 with 4 independent molecules per asymmetric unit. All atoms of the macrocycle core were clearly determined with the structure solution. The alkyl chains could be partially seen and additional atoms were added from the peaks list. The chains are incomplete and the terminal carbons were treated as methyl groups. Refinement was done using both SHELXL-2013 and Olex2 1.3a (Dolomanov 2016). The atoms of the macrocycle core were well-behaved whereas the thermal motion of the alkyl chains were larger, (as expected). The structure contains large solvent accessible voids (63%) arranged as channels running in all three axial directions. Platon Squeeze protocol was applied (Spek 2014). The crystal data have been deposited with the CSD (Table S3).

Table S3. Crystallographic data for C-3BFI

Species	C-3BFI
CCDC No.	2101317
Formula*	C172 H138 N12 O48
Formula weight*	3140.94
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> -1
Crystal size (mm)	0.12x0.12x0.20
Crystal color and shape	Orange prism
Temperature (K)	100
Wavelength (Å)	1.54184
a (Å)	25.6961(3)
b (Å)	25.7044(3)
c (Å)	28.9294(5)
α (°)	99.429(1)
β (°)	104.033(1)
γ (°)	100.553(1)
Volume (Å ³)	17784.5(4)
Z	2
ρ_{calcd} , (g cm ⁻³)	0.586
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.362
No. of reflections (unique)	419200(62062)
R_{int}	0.0478
Completeness to θ (%)	99.2
Data/restraints/parameters	62062/167/2054
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.581
Final R_1 and wR_2 indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	0.1369, 0.3815
R_1 and wR_2 indices (all data)	0.1646, 0.4044

*Formula and weight derived from the crystal structure

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